

Double Boundary Formation on Electrolysis in a W-tube : Theory and its Verification

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Manuscript received 21 August 1976, accepted 17 March 1977

Electrolysis in W-tube type cells has earlier been reported to result in the formation of two sharp and stationary boundaries separating the entire electrolyte into three distinct zones, coloured alkaline, neutral water and coloured acidic (for coloured electrolytes). Herein, a theory has been offered in terms of 'sweeping out of one ion by another' to explain this double boundary formation phenomenon. A number of experimental consequences and confirmations of the theory have been discussed.

It has been reported by Palit^{1,2} that electrolysis of coloured electrolytes (for example, dyes and potassium dichromate solutions) in W-tube type cells results in formation of two sharp and stationary boundaries P and Q (as shown in Figure 1) dividing the entire solution into three zones of contrasting colour and pH—coloured alkaline (CP), colourless neutral water (PQ) and coloured acidic (QA). The phenomenon referred to as 'double boundary formation' has been found to be a usual feature of electrolysis in W-tube type cells. Herein a mechanism has been advanced to explain this novel observation in terms of 'sweeping out' of ions of the electrolyte by ions of the solvent (viz. protons and hydroxyl ions in the case of aqueous systems).

continues, more and more acid and alkali are liberated and within a short time they get uniformly distributed in the corresponding electrode limbs but only up to the points Q and P respectively. Thus the boundaries at these two points remain stationary on continuation of the electrolysis. As the solution is further electrolysed, the regions AQ and PC become increasingly concentrated in acid and alkali respectively whereas the central region QP maintains practically the same ionic strength and pH as at the initial state. The situation remains so as long as the current carriers are ions of the original electrolyte. However, after a period, the duration of which depends on the ionic strength of the original electrolyte and the current strength at which it is being electrolysed, a state is reached when the protons in AQ and hydroxyl ions in PC attain sufficient charge-transport capacity to make a substantial contribution to the total charge-carriers. As electrolysis proceeds, these two ions increasingly take part in the conduction of current at least in AQ and PC, and a stage is reached when a very high percentage of the total current is transported by these two ions. In course of the above physical processes associated with electrolysis, zones of varying conductances are being formed giving rise to varied distribution of potential gradient across the entire cell.

Theory

Ion Migration Pattern—Consequent on electrolysis of an electrolyte (MX) like, potassium dichromate, acid and alkali are generated at the anode and cathode respectively. Now, within a short time the acid and alkali get uniformly mixed-up entirely in their respective vertical electrode limbs and somewhat beyond upto the two points P and Q. This can be tested using indicators. Thus at Q and P two boundaries—one between acidic/neutral and the other between neutral/alkaline solutions, get developed. As electrolysis

Let us now examine what would happen in the intermediate region bounded by P and Q when the protons in AQ and hydroxyl ions in PC become the predominant charge carriers. So long the sole carriers are ions of the original electrolyte, equal number of the same ions are getting in and getting out of this region and as such the region records no change. But as soon as the protons and hydroxyl ions take over the current transport in AQ and PC respectively, the situation in PQ also starts changing. Now, across P enters a flow of negative charge comprising X^- and OH^- , whereas the charge that is swept out across P consists purely of X^- . Thus at the onset of this process, a very thin lamina of solution (containing carried over X^- and OH^-) sandwiched between neutral and alkaline electrolytes, can be conceived to be formed at P. In the next stage, two things could happen. Firstly the layer just above

that at P will attain the anionic composition of that at P in the above way and secondly the layer at P will now have an anionic composition with a higher-fraction of OH^- . Thus as electrolysis proceeds, the thin layer of mixed anionic composition would be advancing and expanding towards Q, and at the same time getting more and more enriched in OH^- and depending on the current strength and anionic composition, a time will be reached when the anions in the entire PQ zone will be almost all OH^- ions. In other words the advancing OH^- ions would as it were be sweeping out the other anions from the intermediate zone PQ. This advancement can proceed only upto Q as beyond it the only anion under the present system that can exist is X^- and across the boundary at Q a change in the anionic current carrier occurs because OH^- ions are coming in and gets replaced by an equivalent number of X^- ions.

Simultaneously with the above process a similar sequence of events takes place at Q in which protons gradually take over the cationic current carriage from M^+ ions and eventually sweep out the cations. As a consequence the zone PQ would eventually contain almost exclusively protons and hydroxyl ions and this zone remains separated from the catholyte CP and anolyte AQ by demarcation of two boundaries at P and Q. Thus the zone PQ is virtually a water zone (trace ionic impurities may be admixed) and the major part of the applied voltage drops over this region and the current reading falls to a low value. So, the whole solution gets now stratified into the three zones viz. the alkaline catholyte (CP), neutral water (PQ) and acidic anolyte (QA) demarcated by the two sharp boundaries at P and Q; for potassium dichromate the colour sequences would be lemon yellow-colourless-orange yellow as observed in practice.

Experimental

Some direct experimental consequences and confirmations of the above theory of double boundary formation are discussed below.

(i) *Colourless band formation at P*: If some highly concentrated electrolyte having the anion different from X^- be added at cathode before beginning the electrolysis, our theory predicts that a thin band of solution enriched with the new anion but depleted in X^- should be formed just above P on electrolysis and this will then advance and extend upto Q. This has been confirmed by adding concentrated H_2SO_4 , Na_2SO_4 or NaOH at cathode to dilute $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution when within a few seconds of the start of electrolysis a distinctly visible perfectly colourless thin band (PP') forms at P (Fig. 2). With further electrolysis, this band expands up to Q when the entire section PQ becomes colourless.

(ii) *Deep coloured band formation at Q*: If the above operation be done at the anode, the theory predicts that a thin band of a solution enriched with

X^- should develop at Q. The layer should also get more and more enriched with X^- with electrolysis. This has been confirmed by adding the aforementioned electrolytes to dichromate solution at anode when a thin band of orange colour (Q'Q) makes its appearance at Q within few seconds of the start of electrolysis (Fig. 3). With time the band gets deeper and deeper. Of course this accumulation stops with exhaustion of dichromate ion in the QC area, when the deep band expectedly smears out into the QA area to have a uniform shade (since the ions that would be swept out from this deep band section are X^- ions).

(iii) *Double band formation*: In fact, if such extra electrolyte addition be made both at the cathode and the anode, the deep band (Q'Q) at Q as well as the colourless band (PP') at P appears in a few seconds simultaneously on switching on the electrolysis (Fig. 4). It is obvious that such electrolyte addition at one or both the electrodes provides us with a technique for quick double boundary formation (about 30 minutes against several hours or overnight by the usual method).

(iv) *Band formation in outermost limbs*: If initially the section KPQL (vide Fig. 5) be filled with a mixture of the coloured electrolyte (e. g. potassium dichromate) and concentrated additional electrolyte (e. g. sodium sulphate), the rest being filled with the dichromate solution alone, and the system be electrolysed, the theory predicts the following. A colourless lamina (L'L) at L and a concentrated band (KK') at K should appear. The point has been borne out by experiments (Fig. 5). Also as expected from the theory, the development of such a coloured or colourless thin band does not occur, if the entire solution be initially a mixture for example of potassium dichromate and sodium sulphate.

(v) *Band formation (colourless at Q and deep coloured at P)*: If the cell be filled up with a cationic dye solution (for visual demonstration purpose) and an additional electrolyte like concentrated sodium sulphate at cathode or anode or both be added as in (i), (ii) or (iii), a deep coloured band (PP') at P or a colourless band (Q'Q) at Q or both (as the case may be) are expected from theory. This has been confirmed experimentally with crystal violet solution (Fig. 6).

(vi) *Deionization in the central zone*: In only those systems where protons from the anodic section and hydroxyl ions from the cathodic section can partake in sweeping out cations and anions respectively in the PQ zone, the current reading should record a gradual fall during the build-up of double-boundary formation. This has also been verified experimentally.

(vii) *Double boundary formation in a simple U-tube*: Suppose the bend section of a simple U-tube (PQ of Fig. 7) be filled with a coloured electrolyte

such as potassium dichromate to which enough sugar has been added to make the solution sufficiently heavy and the rest be filled with the same dichromate solution without sugar to make a sharp separation at P and Q, and the system be electrolysed. According to the foregoing reasoning it should result in double boundary formation in which the section PQ would be colourless (Fig. 7), as now the alkaline/neutral and neutral/acidic boundaries could form at P and Q respectively. This has been found to be so experimentally. Further, as expected, this double boundary formation can be quickened by adding extra electrolyte such as sodium sulphate at the cathode (in the case of a coloured anion) in the same way as in a W-tube.

The mechanism thus proposed in term of 'sweeping out' of the ions in the intermediate zone by other ions (usually H^+ and OH^- unless others are intentionally added) in the other zone, explains satisfactorily all salient features associated with electrolysis in W-tube type cells and predicts a few novel results which have also been experimentally confirmed.

References

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